

TO STUDY THE STRUCTURE OF AVENACINE A-1 AND QUERCETINE USING IR-SPECTROSCOPIC AND QUANTUM-CHEMICAL COMPUTATIONAL TECHNIQUES AND THEIR ANTIMYCOBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

In the countries of the world, special attention is paid to the synthesis of new chemical compounds for medicine. Chemicals compound in the plant such as avenacine A-1, quercetin have the necessary pharmacological effects on the body and therefore act as a natural anti-tuberculosis agent. To obtain effective anti-tuberculosis drugs based on them indicates the need for widespread use of modern quantum chemical methods in conducting cost-effective scientific research based on available raw materials.

Tuberculosis an infectious disease caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis, is one of the largest global problems in the World Health Organization. More than 100 000 people a year suffer from the disease and more than two million people die. The fact that it does not affect antibiotics has led to an increase in the number of drug-resistant and completely drug-resistant strains of the causative agent of tuberculosis Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB), which is resistant to many drugs. The creation of a new drug by chemical synthesis or by studying the composition of biologically active compounds and plants is a very urgent task. Medicinal plants have been used for centuries to treat various diseases, including tuberculosis. Medicinal plant parts such as leaves, roots, root bark, root, flowers and fruit tincture have been used by people around the world for centuries as a traditional remedy for TB.

A wide range of substances for the activity of tuberculosis treatment are such natural compounds as: alkaloids, glycosides, tannins, phenols, Quinones, steroids, triterpenoids. These chemicals contained in the plant have the necessary pharmacological effect on the body and therefore act as a natural anti-tuberculosis agent.

Oats (*Avena* spp.) among plants, the antimicrobial triterpene decomposes with the production of glycosides (saponins). It is able to synthesize several types of avenacin a-1, b-1, a-2 and b-2. In the roots of oats, mainly avenacin a-1 is found.

Avenacin A1 belongs to the class of inorganic compounds, these are sulfites of alkali metals. It is the largest oxoanion in inorganic substances, it is considered a sulfite, and the heaviest atom is an alkali metal. Boiling point 228-233 oC. Solubility: soluble in MeOH and EtOH, poor soluble in H₂O, Et₂O (0.29 g / l) [1; 2].

Quercetin (QUE) -3,3',4',5,7 the molecular mass of a pentagidroxylflavone substance is equal to 302.236 gr / mol, the boiling temperature of which is 316 oC yellow

Quercetin has antioxidant, anticancer properties and broad spectrum biological effect against inflammation, diabetes and microbes [3; 4; 5; 6].

Avenacine A-1, quercetin have pharmacological effects on the body and therefore act as a natural anti-tuberculosis agent. To obtain effective anti-tuberculosis drugs based on them indicates the need for widespread use of modern quantum chemical methods in conducting cost-effective scientific research based on available raw materials. Especially important is the effective use of quantum chemical methods, the study of biological activity, structure and chemical composition in the creation of new

crystalline substance. The chemical formula of quercetin is $C_{12}H_{10}O_7$, the structure of which is presented below:

generations of compounds with such substances as avenacin A-1 and quercetin.

Results and discussion

In order to determine the composition and structure of the isolated avenacine and quercetin AGILENT technology Cary 630 IQ spectrometer, IR spectra were used for determined. The vibration spectrum of the molecular structure of these compounds was calculated by optimizing the DFT/B3LYP method of the Gaussian 98 quantum-chemical calculation program on the basis of 3-21G. In the optimization of molecules, the key words frequency, were used in the calculation of the spectrum of Optimization, vibration (fig.1,2).

Fig.1. Optimized molecular structure of avenacine A-1.

Fig.2. Optimized molecular structure of quercetin. A comparative analysis of the vibration spectra of the compounds was carried out, which was determined by experimental method and calculated

theoretically using the application.

In order to facilitate the research of IR-spectrum results, the rings in the molecules were conditionally numbered. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Results of IR-spectroscopic analysis of Avenacine A-1 and quercetin.

Type of vibration	Avenacine A-		Type of vibration	quercetin	
	calculated, cm^{-1}	determined, cm^{-1}		calculated cm^{-1}	determined, cm^{-1}
$\delta_s(COO)_{8-9}$ between ring	650	652	$\pi(CCC)_{(Ar)1}$ -in the ring	676	670
$\pi(CH)_{(Ar)9}$ - in the ring	875	875	$\pi(CCC)_{(pyran)2}$ - in the ring	717	719
$\square(CH)_{(Cyclohexane)4-5}$ in the ring	1040	1043	$\delta_s(CCC)_{(Ar)3}$ - in the ring	793	793
$\nu_{as}(CC)_{2}$ - in the ring	1081	1084	$\pi(CH)_{(Ar)3}$ - in the ring	875	879
$\delta_{as}(CH)_{(Cyclohexane)6}$ - in the ring	1325	1323	$\delta_s(CCC)_{(Ar)1}$ - in the ring	1009	1010
$\nu_{as}(CCC)_{(Ar)9}$ - in the ring	1374	1382	$\nu_{as}(CO)(CC)_{(pyran)2}$ - in the ring	1075	1092
$\nu_s(CO)_{2}$ - in the ring	1646	1640	$\delta_s(Ar-OH)_{1}$ - in the ring	1162	1162
$\nu_s(C-N)_{(Ar)9}$ - in the ring	2961	2978	$r(CH)_{(Ar)1}$ - in the ring	1260	1259
$\nu_s(OH)$	3261	3350	$\nu_{as}(CCC)_{(Ar)3}$ - in the ring	1374	1379
			$r(CH)_{(pyran)2}$ - in the ring	1393	1405
			$\nu_{as}(CCC)_{(Ar)3}$ - in the ring	1559	1561
			$\nu_{as}(CCC)_{(Ar)1}$ - in the ring	1606	1602
			$\nu_s(CO)_{(pyran)2}$ - in the ring	1646	1658

			$V_{s(C=C)(\text{pyran})2-}$ in the ring	1715	1882
			$V_{s(OH)}$	3103	3268

From the table above, it is possible to see that the IR-spectra obtained by experimental (fig.3, 4) and quantum-chemical computation method of avenacine A-1 and quercetin we can see areas of absorption and vibrations of the bonds, are closer together. The absorption peak of avenacine A-1 with a high intensity in the calculated IR-spectrum 650 cm^{-1} field corresponds to the scissoring deformation ($\delta_{s(COO)}$) vibration of the carboxyl group (COO) bonds in the molecule.

875 cm^{-1} , 1374 cm^{-1} , 2961 cm^{-1} areas intensity low absorption peaks 9-benzene aromatic ring respectively Wagging deformation of C-H bonds ($\pi_{(CH)(Ar)}$), Asymmetric Stretch of C-C-C bonds ($v_{as(CCC)(Ar)}$), Symmetric Stretch of C-N bonds and ($v_{s(C-N)(Ar)}$) belong to Valence vibrations.

1040 cm^{-1} the high peak of intensity in the field corresponds to the rocking deformation vibration ($(CH)(\text{cyclohexane})$) of the bonds C-H of the 4 - and 5-rings.

1081 cm^{-1} , 1325 cm^{-1} , 1646 cm^{-1} area intensity low peaks correspond to asymmetric valence vibration ($v_{as(CCC)}$), of C-C-C bonds in 2-ring, scissoring deformation vibration ($\delta_{as(CH)(\text{cyclohexane})}$) of C-H bonds in 6-ring, symmetric valence vibration ($v_{s(CO)}$) of C-O bonds in 2-ring. The results determined by the experimental way also correspond to the results calculated above.

Also, the calculated IR-spectrum intensity of Quercetine is 676 cm^{-1} , 1009 cm^{-1} , 1260 cm^{-1} areas high absorption peaks 1-

the C-C-C bonds in the benzene ring correspond to wagger deformation vibrations ($\pi_{(CCC)(Ar)}$), scissors vibrations ($\delta_{s(CCC)(Ar)}$), rocking deformation vibration ($r_{(CH)(Ar)}$), 717 cm^{-1} , 1393 cm^{-1} areas intensity low absorption peaks, 1075 cm^{-1} , 1646 cm^{-1} , 1715 cm^{-1} areas intensity high absorption peaks 2 C-C-C, C-H, C-O, C=C bond in pyridine Ring correspond respectively to wagging ($\pi_{(CCC)(pyran)}$), rocking ($r_{(CH)(pyran)}$) deformation vibrations, asymmetric ($v_{as(CO)(CC)(pyran)}$), symmetric ($v_{s(C=C)(pyran)}$ and $v_{s(C=C)(pyran)}$) valence vibration, experimentally determined results are also almost similar to them.

Also calculated 793 cm^{-1} , 875 cm^{-1} and 1374 cm^{-1} , 1559 cm^{-1} the absorption peaks in the fields respectively represent deformation and valence vibrations of the bonds in the 3-benzene ring, and the detected results correspond to this.

It can be concluded that the peak of absorption of both substances in the experimental determined IR-spectrum, respectively 3350 cm^{-1} and 3268 cm^{-1} area is correspond to the valence vibration of the ten groups of molecules, and from the width of the absorption area is weak internal molecular hydrogen bonding in molecules.

IR-spectrum data is consistent with the results of mass-spectrometry analysis.

The values of the peaks formed in the Mass-spectrum are presented in the table below.

Table 2

Mass-spectrometric indicators of Avenasin A

No	Formula	m/z	intensity %
1.	C ₃₅ H ₅₃ O ₉ ⁺	617	100
2.	C ₃₅ H ₅₃ O ₈ ⁺	601	97
3.	C ₃₆ H ₄₇ O ₆ ⁺	575	85
4.	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ O ₉ ⁺	281	35

When measuring the boiling temperature of the separated avenacine A-1, it was shown that the indicator was 232°C. It can be seen that the avenacine A-1 obtained by separating the result is similar with the standard avenacine A-1 indicator.

The obtained IR-spectrum data is also confirmed by the results of mass-spectrometry analysis (fig.5).

The values of the peaks formed in the Mass-spectrum of quercetin are given in Table 3.

Table 3.

Mass-spectrum data of Quercetine

Formula	Molecular ion	Standard		Isolated quercetin	
		m/z	intensity	m/z	intensity
C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	M+[H ₂ O]			287.1180	670.73
C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	[M-H] ⁻	301,19	1092	301.1017	1185.83
C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	(M+H) ⁺	302,08	3606	302.1016	2313.30
C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	(M+H) ⁺	303,06	9169	303.1166	70820.63
C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	(M+H) ⁺	304,05	1373	304.1198	10528.47
C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	(M+H) ⁺	305,01	5205	305.1220	1028.73
C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	(M+Na) ⁺	317,02		317.1348	1177.87

The results of the research showed that the isolated avenacine A-1 and quercetin substances were very close to each other in the areas of absorption in the IR spectra, which were determined experimentally and calculated using the quantum-chemical method of calculation. The obtained IR-spectrum data were also confirmed by the results of mass-spectrometry analysis. This can be based on the conclusion that the

isolated substances are completely compatible with the above molecular structures of avenacine A-1 and quercetin. The minimum inhibition concentration of quercetin was 6.25 Ms_Rv2349c and H37Rv 12.5 ug/ml for Ms_Vec. The mycobacterial inhibition of quercetin, which are presented in the graph indicate its activity against Mycobacterium tuberculosis (figure 3).

Fig.3. Minimal inhibition concentration of QUE.

Quercetin's antimicrobial activity was studied, its effect diameter was 17.8 mm for Ms_Vec and for Ms_Rv 2349 15.7 mm and H37Rv 15.6 mm. Quercetin has an antibacterial activity against M. tubululosis, which may be due to the fact that its biosynthesis of the mycobacterial host wall is carried out by inhibiting enzymes. According to the results of the research conducted by scientists, it was found that quercetin manifests its antimicobacterial activity by inhibiting β

subunits of tubularosis bacteria DNA Girase enzymes[7].

Also, some data suggest that quercetin inhibits the development of mycobacteria by inhibiting enzymes of beta-ketoacyl ACP synthase III [8].

Glycooxalate, which plays an important role in the survival of macrophage, carries out antibacterial activity by inhibiting shunt enzymes isositratliase [9].

Avenasin a-1 was also showed antibacterial activity such as quercetin, and the results obtained were presented in Figure 4.

Fig.4. Antibacterial property of Avenacine

It can also be seen that the antibacterial activity of Avenacine A-1 is 18.4 mm Ms_Rv2349c 16.4 mm and H37Rv 15.7 mm for Ms_Vec, it was found that the bacterial effect on E.coli was higher than on

mycobacteria. It is also possible that the antibacterial property of avenacin was manifested by the exchange of bacterial membrane stucture by the conversion of membrane cholesterol into porous substances (figure 5) [10].

Fig.5. Formation of porous on the double layer of the membrane under the effect of Avenacine A-1

From the results obtained, we can see that all substances have anti-bacterial properties. In particular, we can see that

this indicator is a bridge in the avenacine A-1 substance and that its inhibitory diameter is 15.7 mm for H37Rv, 16.4 mm for MsRv2349c, and is equal to 18.4 mm for Msmegmatis and has a high activity relative to other compounds figure 6.

Fig.6. Antibacterial activity of avenacine and quercetin.

Studies have shown that avenacin, quercetin have activity against tuberculosis mycobacteria.

Method

Quercetine isolation.

For isolation of Quercetine the E.V.Gella. method was used [11] For this, 15 grams of food additive "Astosh" was extracted using 96% ethanol, and the starch was filtered and repeated this process 3 times with increased residue. Then combined the filtrates and dried. Dissolved the dried mass twice in 100 ml of boiling acidic ethanol and re-crystallized in a thermostat at 35 °C.

Then we washed the sediment with distilled water and dried it in a vacuum.

Isolation of Avenacine A-1. Avenacine were isolated by using X.Meyzel's method with some modifications [12]. To do this, the extraction using a reversible refrigerator in a water bath at 80°C for 2 hours with ethanol was conducted centrifuge, made extraction and added filtered water. Minutes at +4°C of the falling precipitate, passed through the centrifuge at a speed of 14000 and dried in an accumulator, collecting the substance.

Mass spectrometry and potentiometry methods

The structure of the compounds IR spectroscopic analysis was performed on a 400-4000 cm^{-1} spectrometer in "Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two", produced in Germany, , "Agilent" spectrometer was performed in the method of Fury in the range of 650-4000 cm^{-1} . Mass spectrometric research was carried out by ionizing with the help of nitrogen molecular ions in the "Perkin Elmer фирмасининг AxION 2 TOF".

Quantum-chemical calculations were carried out on the basis of the Gaussian 98 programming package DFT/b3lyp hybrid method 3-21G. To calculate the molecular optics and IR spectra of chemicals, a 6-31G (2d) base of the DfT/B3LYP hybrid method was used.

Determination of the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of drugs against *avenas*, quercetin and tuberculosis.

Minimum inhibitor concentrations (MIC) [13] were determined after 3 days incubation at 37°C with the help of nitrogen dilution using the method[14]. From the

extract of the tested substances of different concentrations and 100 mml of bacterial suspension were used. After incubation, the lowest concentration of anti-microbial agents was determined as MIC, with a visible increase in the level of micro organism.

Statistical analysis

Each experiment was completed with a minimum of three times. Student's t-criterion was used to analyze significant differences. GraphPad Prism 7 was used to analyze the differences between the experimental groups and the control groups. P value less than 0,05 was considered important.

Competing Interests

No Competing Financial or Non-Financial Interests.

Data availability

All data generated and analyzed during this study are included in this published article. Contributions

I.M conceived the idea of the experiment. Experimental data were taken by I.M. Data analysis was performed by I.M. The paper was written by I.M.

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